

Popular Article

Chemical and Technological application of Protein Based Fat Replacers in Food

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Introduction

Fat is an important constituent of food. So, in the food component, it contributes an important role in sensory and physiological benefits. Fat contributes various functions like flavour, mouthfeel, taste, and aroma/odour (Lucca and Tepper, 1994; Mistry, 2001; Sampaio, 2004). In addition, fat also contributes to other functions such as creaminess, appearance, palatability, texture and glossiness of foods and increases the feeling of satiety during meals (Romanchik-Cerpovicz, 2002; Sipahioglu, 1999). Fat can carry lipophilic flavour compounds, act as a precursor for flavour development and help to stabilize the flavour in food (Romeih, 2002; Tamime, 1999).

Fat Replacer

A fat replacer is an ingredient that can be used to provide all the functions of fat and it also contributes fewer calories. Fat replacers are able to replicate some or all of the functional properties of fat in a fat modified food (Schwenk and Guthrie, 1997).

Types of fat replacer

Fat replacers are classified into two groups: fat substitutes and fat mimetic. Fat substitutes are lipid-like substances proposed to replace the fat on a mass-to-mass basis. Fat mimetics are protein or carbohydrate ingredients which imitate the various functions such as physical, textural, mouth feel and organoleptic properties of true fats (Owusuapenten, 2005). Fat substitutes are further classified into two types such as emulsion and structural lipids. Similarly, fat mimetics are also classified into two types such as microparticulate protein and microparticulate carbohydrates.

Protein Based Fat mimetics

The protein in fat replacement is determined by the degree of denaturation, which affects flavour, as well as the protein solubility, gelling properties and temperature stability. Proteins are responsible for whipping agents, emulsion stabilizers, and dough formation. The fat mimetics are derived from various protein sources like whey, egg, milk, soy, gelatine, wheat gluten and corn zein. Protein-based fat mimetics are commonly used in many forms like butter, cheese, dairy products, salad dressings, sour cream, mayonnaise containing products, soups, sauces, baked goods, and frozen desserts. These protein-based fat mimetics are generally giving a better mouthfeel than carbohydrate-based replacer.

Many protein-based fat mimetics are used in foods and their applications-

Type of fat replacer	Commercial names	Applications
Microparticulated Protein	Simplese®	Milk and milk products (ice cream, butter, sour cream, yogurt, cheese), Baked goods, salad dressings, frozen desserts, mayonnaise type products, margarine, coffee creamer, soups, sauces
Modified Whey Protein Concentrate	Dairy Lo™	Dairy Products, mayonnaise-type products, baked foods, frostings, salad dressing
Others	K-Blazer®, ULTRA-BAKETM, ULTRA-FREEZETM, Lita®, Trailblazer	Frozen desserts, baked foods, spreads, butter, salad dressing

Microparticulated Protein (Simplese®) properties

Microparticulated Protein is manufactured from whey protein concentrate by the patented micro-particulation process. In this process, these are undergone heating and blending, egg protein and milk protein are combined and formed into minute particles and their size are 1–1.5 mm. These particles are spherical and smooth, which allows the mouth to perceive them as fat. The product was introduced by the NutraSweet Corporation in 1988. Simplese® replacer is approved for use as a thickener or texturizer in ice creams and other frozen dessert dairy products by FDA GRAS in the year 1990. This replacer is also suitable for use in many dairy products like yogurt, cheese spreads, cream cheese, and sour cream as well as use for oil-based products such as salad dressings, mayonnaise, and margarine. The caloric value of Simplese® replacer is 1–2 kcal/g. It used for flavour and fatlike creaminess. It is made from proteins, so it cannot be used in foods that require high-temperature applications like frying or baking. When Simplese® replacer is heated, then protein gel and texture effects are lost. People who are allergic to milk proteins may have an allergic reaction to this fat replacer.

Modified Whey Protein Concentrate (Dairy Lo™) properties

Modified whey protein concentrate (Dairy-Lo) is manufactured from high-quality whey protein concentrate and it is recognized as generally recognize as safe (GRAS), Dairy Lo™ contributes 4 kcal/g.

Modified whey protein helps in various forms to improve texture, flavour and stability of low-fat foods. It is used in many dairy products like sour cream, frozen dairy desserts, cheese, yogurts and sauces. Its ability to prevent shrinkage and iciness in frozen dairy foods makes it desirable as a fat replacement ingredient in those products.

Other protein-based fat mimetics

Other than Simplese® and Dairy Lo™, there are other recently developed fat replacers: It is derived from xanthan gum, egg white, whey protein and LITA from Corn Zein.

Application in dairy foods

In the prepared dairy products such as low-fat cheese using Simplese® fat replacer, it was found that Simplese® had an improving effect on cheese appearance (Romeiha *et al.*, 2002). Yazici and Akgun, (2004) has used Simplese® and Dairy Lo™ replacer in yoghurt preparation and it was found good appearance, flavour and colour score to Dairy Lo™ than Simplese®. The Simplese® D-100 and Raftilines HP can improve the sensory and texture properties of low-fat fresh kashar cheese (Koca and Metin, 2004). Zoulias *et al.*, (2002) has analysed textural properties of low-fat cookies. They have reported that an increase in polydextrose or Dairytrim content resulted in harder cookies, while an increase in C-deLight, Simplese® or Raftiline content has the opposite effect. So, C deLight, Simplese® or Raftiline could be used as fat replacers to prepare tenderer lowfat cookies. It was also found that the increase in brittleness of the cookies with increase of all fat mimetics, but a moderate increase was obtained with C-deLight, Simplese® or Raftiline. The whey protein-based fat replacer on sensory characteristic of low fat and non-fat Ice cream (Prindiville *et al.*, 2000). The Simplese® was more similar to milk fat than Dairy Lo™ in its effect on brown colour, cocoa flavour, cocoa character, and textural stability but was less similar in terms of thickness and mouth coating.

Conclusion

A fat replacer is an ingredient can be used in food to provide all the functions of fat. Fat replacers are able to replicate some or all of the functional properties of fat in a fat modified food. It was concluded that the fat replacer is imitating the various functional properties of food such as physical, textural, mouth feel and organoleptic properties of true fats.

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